

Supplementary Information

Disease as a Mediator of Somatic Mutation - Fitspan Coevolution: Model Analysis and Empirical Tests

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We conduct an interior equilibrium existence analysis, and a local stability analysis of the interior equilibrium of the system

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{M} &= aQ - dMF \\ \dot{F} &= vQ - gF - rMF.\end{aligned}$$

A positive interior equilibrium exists when

$$Q > 0, \quad d > 0, \quad g > 0, \quad \text{and} \quad S = dv - ar > 0,$$

in which case

$$M^* = \frac{ag}{S} \quad \text{and} \quad F^* = \frac{vQ}{dg}.$$

There are two main cases in which the interior equilibrium does not exist.

If $S < 0$ and $g > 0$ then setting $M = 0$ yields a boundary equilibrium

$$(M, F) = \left(0, \frac{vQ}{g}\right),$$

which, if $a \leq 0$, is locally stable. Should $a > 0$, then evaluating \dot{M} at this point yields

$$\dot{M}|_{(0, vQ/g)} = aQ > 0,$$

implying trajectories enter the interior ($M > 0, F > 0$).

For sufficiently large M , $rMF \gg gF$ in \dot{F} , so

$$\dot{F} \approx vQ - rMF, \quad F \approx \frac{vQ}{rM}.$$

Substituting into \dot{M} gives

$$\dot{M} = aQ - dM \left(\frac{vQ}{rM} \right) = Q \left(a - \frac{dv}{r} \right).$$

Since $a - dv/r > 0$,

$$M(t) \sim Q \left(a - \frac{dv}{r} \right) t, \quad F(t) \sim \frac{v}{r \left(a - \frac{dv}{r} \right)} t^{-1}, \quad (t \rightarrow \infty),$$

22 that is, SMR grows to infinity and fitspan to zero.

23 If on the other hand, $g = 0$, then the system becomes

$$\dot{M} = aQ - dMF, \quad \dot{F} = vQ - rMF.$$

24 No finite interior equilibrium exists except in the degenerate case $S = vd - ar = 0$, for which the
 25 nullclines coincide ($MF = \text{const}$), whereas for $S \neq 0$ trajectories do not converge to a finite steady
 26 state: $S < 0$ (most disease control occurring through fitspan reduction) leads to unbounded
 27 growth of M and collapse of F , and $S > 0$ (insufficient fitspan control through disease and
 28 external mortality) leads to the opposite behavior.

29 The local stability analysis requires the determinant and trace of the Jacobian matrix, J^* ,

$$J^* = \begin{pmatrix} -dF^* & -dM^* \\ -rF^* & -(rM^* + g) \end{pmatrix}. \quad (1)$$

30 Its trace T , determinant D , and discriminant Δ are

$$T = \text{tr}(J^*) = -\frac{QS}{g} - g - \frac{agr}{S}, \quad D = \det(J^*) = QS, \quad \Delta = T^2 - 4D. \quad (2)$$

31 If the interior equilibrium exists, then two conditions are required for local asymptotic stability.
 32 First, the determinant must be positive,

$$D = \det(J^*) = QS > 0,$$

33 which holds whenever $Q > 0$ and $S > 0$. Second, the trace must be negative,

$$T = \text{tr}(J^*) = -\left(\frac{QS}{g} + g + \frac{agr}{S}\right) < 0.$$

34 If $r \geq 0$ then the bracketed term is > 0 and the trace is negative. If $r < 0$, then $S = vd - ar =$
 35 $vd + a|r| \geq a|r|$, so $ag|r|/S \leq g$, implying

$$\frac{QS}{g} + g + \frac{agr}{S} = \frac{QS}{g} + g - \frac{ag|r|}{S} \geq \frac{QS}{g} > 0.$$

36 Therefore $T < 0$ holds whenever $S > 0$ and $g > 0$. Thus, the interior equilibrium is always locally
 37 asymptotically stable.

38

39 Returns to Equilibrium: Stable Focus vs Stable Node

40 The condition for a stable focus (damped oscillations to the equilibrium) is

$$\Delta < 0 \quad (3)$$

41 or

$$T^2 < 4QS, \quad (4)$$

42 which, with all parameter substitutions becomes

$$\frac{QS}{g} - 2\sqrt{QS} + \frac{vdg}{S} < 0.$$

43 It can be shown that this inequality can only hold for some $r < 0$ (see below) and all $r > 0$ yield
 44 a stable node.

45 Indeed, if $r < 0$, then a damped oscillatory return to equilibrium can only occur for intermediate
 46 intervals of model parameters:

47
 48

49 **Interval for S**

50 Substituting $S = dv - ar$ into the condition for oscillatory return to equilibrium eliminates r
 51 entirely and yields

$$\frac{QS}{g} + \frac{g dv}{S} < 2\sqrt{QS}. \quad (5)$$

52 The boundary between monotone and oscillatory return is therefore defined by the equality

$$\frac{QS}{g} + \frac{g dv}{S} = 2\sqrt{QS}. \quad (6)$$

53 Let $x = \sqrt{QS}$. The boundary condition becomes

$$\frac{x^2}{g} + \frac{g dv Q}{x^2} = 2x, \quad (7)$$

54 or equivalently

$$x^4 - 2g x^3 + g^2 dv Q = 0, \quad (8)$$

55 which (when it has two positive roots) defines $x_- < x_+$.

56 A simple sufficient (but not necessary) condition for the existence of an oscillatory interval in S is

$$g > \sqrt{Qvd}. \quad (9)$$

57 Transforming back to $S = x^2/Q$, we define

$$S_- = \frac{x_-^2}{Q}, \quad S_+ = \frac{x_+^2}{Q}. \quad (10)$$

58 The interior equilibrium exhibits damped oscillatory return whenever

$$S \in (S_-, S_+), \quad (11)$$

59 and returns monotonically otherwise.

60 This condition shows that oscillatory dynamics are favored by sufficiently small body mass Q ,
 61 weak somatic mutational input (dv), or large extrinsic loss of fitspan (g), whereas large Q or
 62 strong somatic input suppress oscillations.

63 **Interval for r**

64 Since $S = vd - ar$ with $a > 0$, the oscillatory interval $S \in (S_-, S_+)$ maps to

$$r \in (r_-, r_+), \quad r_- = \frac{vd - S_+}{a}, \quad r_+ = \frac{vd - S_-}{a},$$

65 with length $(S_+ - S_-)/a$. The interior equilibrium requires $S > 0$, equivalently $r < vd/a$. A simple
 66 sufficient (but not necessary) condition for the oscillatory interval to exist in S is $g > \sqrt{Qvd}$.

67 Since $r < 0$ if and only if $S > vd$, a damped oscillatory return (stable focus) occurs for

$$r \in \left(\frac{vd - S_+}{a}, 0 \right),$$

68 which is nonempty iff $S_- < vd < S_+$. The oscillatory interval lies entirely in $r < 0$ iff $S_- > vd$.

69 Although not shown here, similar to r , a damped oscillatory return occurs for values of v and d
 70 lying in finite intervals obtained by mapping the oscillatory condition $S \in (S_-, S_+)$ through the
 71 relation $S = dv - ar$.

72 Interval for g

73 Damped oscillations can be shown to occur iff (again, assuming $r < 0$)

$$g \in (g_-, g_+), \quad g_{\pm} = \frac{S}{dv} \left(\sqrt{QS} \pm \sqrt{Qa(-r)} \right),$$

74 with interval length

$$g_+ - g_- = \frac{2S}{dv} \sqrt{Qa(-r)}.$$

75 Interval for Q

76 The Q -interval and its interval length for damped oscillatory returns to equilibrium are, respec-
 77 tively,

$$Q \in (Q_-, Q_+), \quad Q_{\pm} = \frac{g^2}{S^2} \left(\sqrt{S} \pm \sqrt{-ar} \right)^2,$$

78 and

$$Q_+ - Q_- = \frac{4g^2}{S^2} \sqrt{S(-ar)}.$$

79 Return time to equilibrium

80 The characteristic polynomial from the Jacobian is $\lambda^2 - T\lambda + D = 0$, and hence the eigenvalues
 81 are found from

$$\lambda_{1,2} = \frac{T \pm \sqrt{\Delta}}{2}. \quad (12)$$

82 The eigenvalues have negative real parts (locally stable). The eigenvalue of interest for return
 83 following perturbation has the real part closest to 0 (the slowest-decaying mode):

$$\lambda_{\text{slow}} = \frac{T + \sqrt{\Delta}}{2}. \quad (13)$$

84 The time for a small perturbation to shrink by a factor e in the linearized dynamics is the e -fold
 85 time τ_e , defined as

$$\tau_e := \frac{1}{|\Re(\lambda_{\text{slow}})|}, \quad (14)$$

86 where $\Re(\lambda_{\text{slow}})$ denotes the real part of the slowest eigenvalue, which sets the exponential decay
 87 rate of small perturbations in the linearized dynamics. The e -fold time τ_e is the inverse of this

88 rate and is the characteristic time over which a perturbation decays to about 37% of its initial
 89 size ($1/e$).

90 Importantly, the expression for τ_e differs between a stable focus and a stable node. The parameter
 91 effects on return times for a stable focus are much more straightforward than for a stable node.

92 1. Stable focus ($\Delta < 0$)

93 Eigenvalues are complex conjugates with real part $T/2 < 0$, so

$$\tau_{\text{focus}} = \frac{1}{|T|/2} = -\frac{2}{T} = \frac{2}{\frac{QS}{g} + g + \frac{agr}{S}}. \quad (15)$$

94 Thus, long return times following a perturbation are favored by small body size Q . Moreover,
 95 for $r \leq 0$, lower v (less input into somatic function) or lower d (weaker selection against SMR)
 96 monotonically increase the return time.

97 The effects of the remaining parameters (a, r, g) are contingent on the ‘switching condition’: the
 98 reduced numerator of $\partial\tau_{\text{focus}}/\partial x$, where x is any of a, r, g .

$$K = QS^2 - dg^2v,$$

99 such that

$$\text{sign}\left(\frac{\partial\tau_{\text{focus}}}{\partial a}\right) = \text{sign}(r) \text{sign}(K), \quad \text{sign}\left(\frac{\partial\tau_{\text{focus}}}{\partial r}\right) = \text{sign}(K), \quad \text{sign}\left(\frac{\partial\tau_{\text{focus}}}{\partial g}\right) = \text{sign}(K).$$

100 2. Stable node ($\Delta > 0$)

101 The expression for a stable node e-fold return is more complex than for the stable focus:

$$\tau_{\text{node}} = \frac{1}{|\lambda_{\text{slow}}|} = -\frac{1}{\lambda_{\text{slow}}} = -\frac{2}{T + \sqrt{\Delta}} = \frac{2}{\left(\frac{QS}{g} + g + \frac{agr}{S}\right) - \sqrt{\left(\frac{QS}{g} + g + \frac{agr}{S}\right)^2 - 4QS}}. \quad (16)$$

102 Return-time analytics (partial derivatives of τ_{node} with respect to each parameter) are generally
 103 complex. Increasing Q decreases τ_{node} in much of parameter space by increasing $D = QS$ and
 104 making T more negative, whereas a, r , and g can have competing effects through T and S ,
 105 yielding context-dependent changes in τ_{node} .

106 To see parameter effects in more detail, define

$$R = \sqrt{\Delta} = \sqrt{T^2 - 4D}.$$

107 The slow eigenvalue is $\lambda_{\text{slow}} = (T + R)/2 < 0$, and hence the stable-node e-fold index can be
 108 expressed as

$$\tau_{\text{node}} = \frac{1}{|\lambda_{\text{slow}}|} = -\frac{2}{T + R} = \frac{R - T}{2D}.$$

109 A useful sign rule for any parameter x is

$$\text{sign}\left(\frac{\partial\tau_{\text{node}}}{\partial x}\right) = \text{sign}(K_x),$$

110 where K_x , the switching condition of $\partial\tau_{\text{node}}/\partial x$, is obtained by factoring out all strictly positive
 111 terms, whence

$$K_x = (T + R) \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} - 2 \frac{\partial D}{\partial x}.$$

112 Because the remaining multiplicative factors in $\partial\tau_{\text{node}}/\partial x$ are positive in the stable-node region
 113 ($D > 0$, $R > 0$), the sign of K_x alone determines whether increasing parameter x increases or
 114 decreases the node return time.

115 The effects of the parameters a, r, g are contingent on their parameter-specific switching conditions
 116 K_a, K_r, K_g :

$$\text{sign}\left(\frac{\partial\tau_{\text{node}}}{\partial a}\right) = \text{sign}(K_a), \quad \text{sign}\left(\frac{\partial\tau_{\text{node}}}{\partial r}\right) = \text{sign}(K_r), \quad \text{sign}\left(\frac{\partial\tau_{\text{node}}}{\partial g}\right) = \text{sign}(K_g),$$

117 where, as above, $K_x = (T + R)T_x - 2D_x$, and the required partial derivatives are

$$D_a = -Qr, \quad D_r = -Qa, \quad D_g = 0,$$

$$118 \quad T_a = \frac{Qr}{g} - \frac{gr}{S} - \frac{agr^2}{S^2}, \quad T_r = \frac{Qa}{g} - \frac{ag}{S} - \frac{a^2gr}{S^2}, \quad T_g = \frac{QS}{g^2} - 1 - \frac{ar}{S}.$$

119 Thus,

$$K_a = (T + R) \left(\frac{Qr}{g} - \frac{gr}{S} - \frac{agr^2}{S^2} \right) + 2Qr,$$

120

$$K_r = (T + R) \left(\frac{Qa}{g} - \frac{ag}{S} - \frac{a^2gr}{S^2} \right) + 2Qa,$$

121

$$K_g = (T + R) \left(\frac{QS}{g^2} - 1 - \frac{ar}{S} \right).$$

122 For a :

$$\text{If } K_a > 0, \text{ then } \frac{\partial\tau_{\text{node}}}{\partial a} > 0, \quad \text{if } K_a < 0, \text{ then } \frac{\partial\tau_{\text{node}}}{\partial a} < 0.$$

123 For r :

$$\text{If } K_r > 0, \text{ then } \frac{\partial\tau_{\text{node}}}{\partial r} > 0, \quad \text{if } K_r < 0, \text{ then } \frac{\partial\tau_{\text{node}}}{\partial r} < 0.$$

124 For g :

$$\text{If } K_g > 0, \text{ then } \frac{\partial\tau_{\text{node}}}{\partial g} > 0, \quad \text{if } K_g < 0, \text{ then } \frac{\partial\tau_{\text{node}}}{\partial g} < 0.$$

125 In contrast, the impacts of Q, v , and d on τ_{node} are more transparent.

126 For Q

$$D_Q = S > 0, \quad T_Q = -\frac{S}{g} < 0,$$

127 so increasing Q typically decreases τ_{node} by simultaneously increasing D and making T more
 128 negative.

129 Likewise, for v and $r \leq 0$ we have

$$D_v = Qd > 0, \quad T_v = -\frac{Qd}{g} + \frac{agr d}{S^2} \leq 0.$$

130 Similar patterns are found for d . Hence for $r \leq 0$, increasing v or d typically decreases τ_{node} .